

Network Resource Allocation for Gaming Using MEC API and TeraFlowSDN

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Abstract—Multi-access edge computing (MEC) provides IT resources at the edge of the network. Proximity to the users significantly enhances real-time gaming experiences because of the available high-bandwidth and low-latency network connection, which is essential for modern gaming demands. Leveraging TeraFlowSDN (TFS), a cloud-native open-source Software Defined Networking (SDN) controller, we introduce a novel MEC bandwidth management service that extends TFS’s API capabilities to handle standardized bandwidth requests. Our approach facilitates the provisioning of network bandwidth through interaction between an extended open-source gaming client and TFS. This integration enables dedicated bandwidth allocation, prioritizes gaming traffic, and ultimately improves the user experience by delivering high-bandwidth, low-latency services tailored to end-user applications. This work demonstrates a practical, scalable solution for optimizing network resources in latency-sensitive environments like gaming.

Index Terms—software-defined networking (SDN), TeraFlowSDN, Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)

I. INTRODUCTION

When gaming networking is considered, the integration of Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) and network control and management appears as a promising solution [1]. A MEC setup offers ultra-low latency and high bandwidth, in addition to data and radio network data that applications may use in real-time.

The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) MEC Industry Specification Group (ISG) has made significant technical contributions towards the advancement of edge computing. Their work focuses on creating a standardized, open environment for the seamless integration of applications across multi-vendor platforms, which is critical for the efficient deployment and operation of edge computing solutions. Key achievements include the development of a comprehensive framework and reference architecture that supports diverse use cases and interoperability requirements. The MEC Bandwidth Management (BWM) service is for allocating/adjusting bandwidth resources, including bandwidth size and bandwidth priority, for MEC applications, and allows MEC applications to provide bandwidth requirements [2].

ETSI TeraFlowSDN (TFS) is an advanced, open-source, cloud-native Software Defined Networking (SDN) controller developed in the scope of ETSI Software Development Group TeraFlowSDN. The TFS controller leverages a micro-

architecture, enabling high scalability, performance, and flexibility [3].

This demonstration analyses the benefits that MEC BWM and TFS offer in the context of gaming networking. Improved gaming performance, reduced congestion, and increased scalability stand out as key advantages. The prioritization of gaming traffic, facilitated by BWM and TFS, contributes to specific bandwidth allocation and latency reduction, thereby elevating the overall quality of the gaming experience. The allocation of designated bandwidth to gaming applications mitigates network congestion, fostering an improved gaming environment for all users. This integration of MEC BWM and TFS emerges as a valuable tool for network operators aspiring to deliver a dedicated and enhanced gaming experience to their users.

Fig. 1. Proposed demonstration architecture

Fig. 2. Proposed sequence diagram

Fig. 3. a) Moonlight Game Streaming Application Client User Interface [5]; b) Sunshine Game Streaming Application Server [4]; c) Moonlight User Interface Extension developed for MEC 015 BWM network resource allocation request; d) Game streaming after connectivity establishment.

II. DEMO CONTENT AND IMPLEMENTATION

Fig. 1 shows the proposed demonstration architecture, which includes the client, server at the edge, and edge network connecting them. The figure depicts Moonlight client (running on end-user premises) and Sunshine server. Moonlight is the game streaming application client [5] (Fig. 3.a). It allows to play PC games on various devices, through game streaming, as it is an open-source implementation of NVIDIA's GameStream protocol. On the other hand, Sunshine is the game streaming application server [4] (Fig. 3.b). It offers low latency and cloud gaming server capabilities with support for AMD, Intel, and Nvidia GPUs for hardware encoding. Sunshine is run on the edge resources, typically deployed in a Data Centre (DC). The client and server are connected to the edge network which is comprised of two physical IP routers that are directly connected via cable. The routers' management interfaces and TeraFlowSDN (TFS) controller are connected to the management network. Moonlight host is connected to the management and data plane networks. The former connection is used to send the MEC 015 BWM request to TFS and the latter is used for gaming traffic. The Sunshine host is connected to the data plane network for game streaming. TFS host is connected to the management network to receive the MEC 015 BWM requests and configure the IP routers. It can be observed that ETSI TFS acts as an End-to-End (E2E) SDN controller/orchestrator of the network.

The resource allocation workflow is shown in Fig.2. The video of the demo is available in [7]. The primary actor in

this scenario is the user, who can interact with TFS using an extended Moonlight interface (see Fig. 3.c) that can send a MEC BWM request. We enable the open-source Moonlight to send the MEC BWM request by adding a new panel to the software (Fig. 3.c). The scenario starts with the client (extended Moonlight) sending a MEC 015 BWM allocation request to the northbound interface (NBI) endpoint of ETSI TFS developed for this research activity. Upon client request, TFS leverages its service component to orchestrate connectivity establishment workflow. The workflow includes path computation and IP router configuration by PathComp and Device components of TFS. TFS creates the routers' configurations based on the OpenConfig standard data models to configure the routers with border gateway protocol (BGP) for connectivity establishment. TFS pushes the NetConf OpenConfig configurations into routers deployed in the ADRENALINE testbed at CTTC premises [6]. When routers are configured, the service establishment acknowledgment propagates to the client and the bandwidth becomes available for gaming (Fig. 3.d).

We capture the messages sent between Moonlight and TFS via the Wireshark application. The message exchange is shown in Fig. 4. It starts with a TCP handshake between extended Moonlight and TFS in messages 1-3. Then the extended Moonlight sends a MEC 015 BWM request to TFS in message No. 4. The message is an HTTP request that includes a JSON object with MEC 015 BWM compatible fields (Fig. 4). Upon receiving the request, TFS triggers its connectivity establishment workflow, and then TFS responds with a connection establishment acknowledgment in message

Fig. 4. Message exchange capture between extended Moonlight and TFS. Moonlight and TFS IP addresses are 10.1.1.188 and 10.1.1.119, respectively.

No. 6 after 7 seconds.

III. INNOVATION

This section presents the unique aspects of our research activity, detailing how it enhances the experience for users.

Network-tailored Application: Unlike conventional approaches that treat all applications uniformly, MEC BWM and TFS innovate by employing application-triggered requests to the network. This ensures a targeted and responsive allocation of network resources for the most bandwidth-demanding gaming applications. We extend the gaming application (Moonlight) so it can request the necessary network resources.

End-to-End Dynamic and Adaptive Bandwidth Allocation: The integration with TFS enables real-time responsiveness to the changing demands of the packet-optical network. This allocation mechanism ensures that resources are optimally distributed in a multi-layer network, aligning with the diverse performance requirements of different gaming scenarios.

Application-network interface in TFS: Innovation lies in the novel API facilitated by TFS to allow applications to request bandwidth allocation directly. This dynamic allocation ensures that gaming applications receive dedicated and exclusive network services. TFS can monitor in real-time a departure from static allocation methods, offering a proactive approach to safeguard against potential congestion and maintain an uninterrupted gaming experience.

User-Centric Focus: Ultimately, the innovation in MEC BWM and TFS is driven by a user-centric philosophy. By prioritizing gaming applications and tailoring resource allocation to their specific needs, this approach elevates the gaming experience to new heights. Reduced latency, improved performance, and minimized congestion collectively contribute to a network environment that aligns with the expectations and demands of modern gamers.

IV. CONCLUSION

This demonstration will be the first to showcase a direct interaction from a gaming application with the network controller. Moreover, a standardized interface for managing resources at the network edge such as ETSI MEC 015 will be used.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research leading to this publication has been partially financed by the Horizon Europe Hexa-X-II Project (grant agreement No. 101095759) and by Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital and the European Union-Next GenerationEU in the frameworks of the Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia and of the Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia through UNICO-5G I+D 6GMICROSDN project under references TSI-063000-2021-19, TSI-063000-2021-20, TSI-063000-2021-21 MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER/UE and by the RELAMPAGO project (Grant PID2021-127916OB-I00), funded by MICIU/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU.

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